

DETERMINING THE CAUSES OF POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE PERCEPTIONS OF TURKISH HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS ABOUT GERMAN COURSES THROUGH METAPHORS ACCORDING TO THE HIGH SCHOOL TYPE VARIABLE

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Abstract:

Compulsory second foreign language phenomenon has emerged in Turkey in the near term. German was made compulsory as the second foreign language in Anatolian high schools in the academic year 2012-2013. As with the first foreign language teaching, there are also problems with the second foreign language teaching. The revealing of the problems in teaching German as a second foreign language from the perspective of the students, in line with the experiences of the students will provide concrete data. In this context, the aim of this study is to determine in Turkey the causes of positive and negative perceptions of high school students about German course through metaphors according to the high school type variable. To achieve this goal, the phenomenology method, one of the qualitative research approaches, was used. The research group of this study consists of 308 students studying in different high school types in Muğla province in the second semester of the 2018-2019 academic year. The data of this study were obtained from five types of schools: Social sciences, science high school, Anatolia, vocational and technical, private high school. While the most negative categories developed regarding the German course are seen in the social sciences high school; positive categories, on the other hand, were mostly developed in Tourism High School. The perception of Atatürk vocational and Technical Anatolian High School students, which is one of the five schools in which data are obtained, differs compared to other schools. As this school is a Tourism vocational high school, students studying in this school think that, unlike the other four high schools, German lessons are a necessary lesson and this language must be learned. On the other hand, four high school students stated that this lesson was not necessary and that there would be no loss for them. When a general evaluation based on the data obtained is made, the reasons for the negative perceptions of the students about the German course are, it can be said that it depends on the structure of the language,

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student-centered, teacher competence centered, exam system centered, and national language policy centered.

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1. Introduction

In Turkey, both the first foreign language, as well as the language policy adopted in terms of a second foreign language differs from year to year up to the present from the past. Namely, since the 1997-1998 academic year, 5-year compulsory education in Turkey was arranged as 8 years of education. With this arrangement, English has started to take place in the curriculum as of the fourth grade of primary education as the first foreign language. In this period, German was seen as the second foreign language in Science and Anatolian high schools. With the 4 + 4 + 4 changes made in the education system in the 2012-2013 academic year, English education was brought to an earlier level by reducing the teaching of English to an earlier age. All these changes have made arrangements in German teaching as in other courses. These developments have changed the position of the German in the türkische education system in Turkey. In the 2012-2013 academic year, German was made compulsory as the second foreign language in Anatolian high schools. As has been seen the phenomenon of a compulsory second foreign language has been raised recently in Turkey. Previously, it took its place in educational institutions as second foreign language elective. As explained above, English as the first foreign language has preserved its place from past to present. Prioritizing the teaching of English caused the second foreign language education not to be given importance (Akillilar, 2013; Koçak, 2014). In addition, "*the time allocated to the second foreign language course is quite limited compared to the first foreign language course in terms of both weekly class hours and distribution by years*" (Hanbay, 2013: 272). These arrangements influence the importance of teaching German in high schools of different types in Turkey and are decisive in the perception of the students towards German lessons. In this context, the aim of this study is to determine in Turkey the causes of positive and negative perceptions of high school students about German course through metaphors according to the high school type variable. Revealing the disruptions in teaching German as a second foreign language from the perspective of students, in line with the experiences of students, may contribute to obtaining more realistic data. Because in this process, students are the primary people affected by language teaching, which is prepared with many factors such as teacher qualifications, methods, programs, and language policies. This study is important because the problems encountered in teaching German are presented from the perspective of students.

2. Material and Methods

The phenomenon of phenomenology, which is one of the qualitative research approaches, was used in this research, in which students' perceptions of German lessons as a second foreign language were tried to be determined through metaphors according to different high school types. Phenomenology is the perception of events experienced by individuals from the perspectives based on their experience. Phenomenology provides insight into the meaning and nature of everyday experiences. Therefore, any fact or event according to this method; is perceived by beliefs, prejudices, and all other subjective aspects. In addition, the phenomenology method is used to reach more accurate information about the phenomenon to be investigated or what is apparent. Therefore, the essence of the individual's experiences can be reached with this method. In order to interpret the obtained data, interpretive (hermeneutic) phenomenology, one of the research types of phenomenology, was preferred. Interpretive phenomenology serves the purpose of interpreting experiences experienced by individuals (Bal, 2016; Karakoç, 2019; Patton, 2014; Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2008). In this context, in this study, what German lesson meant for them in accordance with the experiences of students studying in different high schools was investigated, and related information was collected and data were interpreted.

2.1. Research Group

The research group of this study consists of 308 students studying in different high school types in Muğla province in the second semester of 2018-2019 academic year. Students from five school types, namely Social Sciences High School, Science High School, Anatolian High School, Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School (Tourism) and Private High School participated in the study.

2.2. Data Collection Tool

The data of the research was obtained with a form prepared as "German lesson for me is like..., because". The form was explained by going to the schools one by one and distributed to the students and the students were provided to understand the expression. The students were asked to write the first concept that comes to mind when they think of German lesson. In addition, the students were asked to write the reasons or reasons for the metaphor they chose regarding the German lesson, and the data were analyzed and interpreted in more detail.

2.3. Data Collection and Analysis

For the analysis of the data, the forms filled out by the students in each school type were numbered separately. The participants were given names such as 9K, 10E in order to determine their grade levels and gender. Content analysis was used in the analysis of the data. As a result of these analyzes, the metaphors developed for the German lesson are

listed separately for each school type. The metaphors listed are divided into conceptual categories, taking into account their justifications. Positive and negative categories were identified and the data were interpreted. Depending on the reasons for the same metaphors, the same metaphor was shown under different categories. In order to understand the data more clearly, the statements of the students are given a place in the findings section. The formula of Miles and Huberman (1994) was used to calculate the reliability of the study. This formula; "Reliability = consensus / consensus + divergence". Accordingly, if the consistency between experts and researcher evaluations is 90% and above, a desired level of reliability is provided (cited in Saban, 2008: 430). Accordingly, the data obtained in each school type and the categories created in line with these data were sent to a field specialist and it was asked to list metaphors under the categories created by the researcher. The matchmaking of the researcher and the specialist was compared, and as a result of the comparison, the "obstacle" metaphor in the category of "very difficult" from the data of Mentese High School of High Schools; "The language I don't need" metaphor in the category of being unnecessary has been taken into the category of "inability to learn". Accordingly, the reliability of Mentese Social Sciences High School data was calculated as $64/64 + 2 \times 100 = \% 97.1$.

From the data of Muğla 75th-year science high school, the "pool" metaphor in the category of "being detailed" has been classified as "inefficient"; the metaphor of "an inefficient lesson" in the "inefficient" category is placed in the "unnecessary" category. Accordingly, reliability of Muğla 75th year High School data was calculated as $41/41 + 2 \times 100 = \% 97.1$.

From the data of Turgut Reis Anatolian High School, in the "unnecessary" category include metaphors of "emptiness and cruelty" fall under the category of "difficult"; the "waffle" metaphor in the "difficult" category has been included in the "learning new things" category. Accordingly, the reliability of Turgut Reis Anatolian High School data was calculated as $53/53 + 3 \times 100 = \% .95$.

The "privilege" metaphor in the category of "being different from other languages" from Technology and Culture College data is placed in the category of "being important". Accordingly, the reliability of Technology and Culture College data was calculated as $27/27 + 1 \times 100 = \% .98$. Therefore, it can be said that the study has a high reliability rate. Field specialist has not changed the data of Atatürk vocational and technical Anatolian high school.

3. Findings

In this section, 66 obtained from Mentese Social Sciences High School; 43 from Muğla 75th year science high school; 56 from Turgut Reis Anatolian High School; 20 from Atatürk vocational and technical Anatolian (tourism school) high school 20; from the High School of Technology and Culture 28 categories were created.

A. Categories of Metaphors Developed by Mentese Social Sciences High School Students Regarding German Lessons

The metaphors developed by Mentese social sciences high school students related to German lessons were gathered under 10 categories as “complex, very difficult, imperative, unloved, demanding effort, unnecessary, creating trauma, not being learned, important, not being taught well”. Each category is explained below.

Table 1: Metaphors and Reasons for Being Complex

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Human emotions	Complex as human emotions	Being complex
Closed box	Difficult to understand	
Space	Don't know where to start	
Nightmare	A language that is difficult to speak and understand	
Obstacle	To be a very different language	

As seen in Table 1, “human emotions, closed box, space, nightmare and obstacle” metaphors were developed in the category of complexity. When the analogy of the metaphors, that is, the reasons, were examined, it was determined that according to students German was very difficult to understand because it had a different and mixed linguistic structure. Participant 9k “*German lesson is a nightmare for me. Because it is a very complex language that is difficult to speak and difficult to understand.*” stated in these words that it was difficult by comparing the structure of German to the nightmare and therefore had difficulties in speaking and understanding German. Participant Hk “*German lessons are like human emotions because human emotions are as complex as German.*” stated that by associating human emotions with German, both of them are complex and difficult to solve.

Table 2: Metaphors and Reasons for the Very Difficult Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Waking from sleep	To be very difficult	To be very difficult
A difficult target	Complex grammatical structure	
War	Being a difficult language	
A difficult way	Being difficult	
Whirlpool	The most difficult of the language lessons	

In the category of being very difficult in Table 2, the metaphors of “waking from sleep, a difficult target, war, a difficult way, and whirlpool” have been developed. When the reasons for the metaphors were examined, it was determined that according to students the grammatical structures of German have a complex feature and that German is very difficult compared to other languages. Participant 11E “*The German lesson is like a vortex for me. Because it is the hardest of the language lessons.*” stated that German is more difficult than English; Participant He “*The German lesson is like waking up mornings because they are*

both very difficult.” in his analogy, he emphasized that the German learning process requires a lot of effort and that it is very difficult in this process.

Table 3: Metaphors and Reason for being obligatory Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
The food I have to eat	Compulsory courses	Being necessary
Program watched when there is nothing to watch on TV	To be obligatory	
Leek	Forced lesson	
To teach the newborn baby a function	Teaching timeless	
Obligation	Compulsory courses	

In Table 3, in the obligatory category, the metaphors of "the food that I have to eat, the program watched when there is nothing to watch on TV, leek, teaching the newborn baby to function, obligation" are developed. When the reasons for the metaphors were examined, it was determined that the students saw German as a lesson learned because they were compulsory, not willingly. Therefore, when they are given the right to choose, it can be said that they do not want to learn German. Participant 9k *“German lesson is like leek for me because I learn German like leek forcibly”* stated that she didn’t learn German voluntarily, she learned German, since it was compulsory; Participant 10e *“The German lesson is like teaching a newborn baby a function because it is being tried to teach German to students who have not yet fully grasped English. I think German should only be taught to those who are interested, so it should be an elective course.”* stated that teaching German as the second foreign language, which is relatively harder than English, before learning English as a first foreign language, is not educationally correct.

Table 4: Metaphors and Reasons for the not being disliked Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
A meal I don't like	Verb conjugation is difficult	Not being disliked
Okra dish	Never like	
Torture	Dislike teacher	
A rude teacher	To be coarse language	
Unnecessary	Poor education	
Book	Indifference	

In the category of not being disliked in Table 4, the metaphors of “a meal that I don’t like, okra dish, torture, a rude teacher, unnecessary, book” were developed. When the reasons for the metaphors are evaluated, it can be concluded that conjugation of names in German language causes negative feelings against the German lesson and this causes the students to lose their interests and motivations. Participant 10e *“The German lesson is like torture for me because our teacher doesn’t teach us anything”* stated with an analogy that German teachers are inadequate in creating an efficient and effective learning environment for them; participant 12k *“the German lesson is an unnecessary lesson for me, because of can not be*

taught despite for five years.” expressed that they did not learn German even though they took German lessons for a total of five years, including preparation plus four years.

Table 5: Metaphors and Reasons for Requiring Effort Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Spoiled child	Requesting attention	Demanding effort
Fishing	To be successful if tried	
Broken toy	Working hard to understand the rules	
High wall	Effortfully Overcoming	
Bobby pin	Learning with effort	
Sea	Learning with effort	

In the category of requiring effort in Table 5, “spoiled child, fishing, broken toy, high wall, bobby pin, sea” metaphors have been developed. According to the reasons for the metaphors, it is understood that according to the students, in order to be successful in German lessons, it is necessary to make a lot of effort and to learn the rules in German by working hard. Participant Hk *“German lesson is like a spoiled child for me. Because the German lesson requires attention and if you don’t care, sometimes you can understand it very well, but sometimes you can not speak at all.”* pointed out that in order to understand the German lesson, it should be very relevant to understand German grammar, and knowing German grammar is not enough to speak German; participant 11k *“The German lesson is like a high wall for me because it can be learned only through effort.”* stated that it is necessary to work hard to understand German with its high wall analogy.

Table 6: Metaphors and Reasons for the Unnecessary Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Cake	Not compulsory	Unnecessary category
An empty lesson	Preferring another language instead of German	
Emptiness	To be meaningless	
An empty container	Being indifferent	
Eat cake	Insignificant	
Unnecessary lesson	Not need-oriented	
Waste of time	Not using German	
Physical education lesson	Insignificant	

Table 6 contains the metaphors of “cake, empty lesson, emptiness, empty container, eating cake, unnecessary lesson, waste of time, physical education lesson” in the unnecessary category. When the reasons for the metaphors are examined, it can be evaluated according to the students that the German lesson is not of vital importance compared to the other lessons, and the absence of a German lesson will not be a deficiency for them. Participant 9e *“German lesson is like an empty container for me. Because if those who study are not interested in German, it will not work.”* stated that students' interests and preferences should also be taken into consideration in language teaching, and those who are not interested in that language may have low motivation; participant 11k *“German*

lesson is like a waste of time for me. Because I will not use it in any area of life, instead of it may be another language such as Russian and Arabic." stated that she would not face German in business life in the future, and she would prefer to learn languages such as Russian and Arabic instead of German.

Table 7: Metaphors and Reason for Creating Trauma Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
A child whose toy was bereaved	Being tearful in the lesson	Creating trauma
Snake	German exam to being bad	
A killing hit	Having a headache during the lesson	
Hitler	Bring a massacre	
Torture	To be boring	
Paralysis	Retribution	
Bodyguard	To be harmed	
The first step taken by the child	Experiencing every emotion while learning	

In Table 7, in the category of creating trauma, metaphors of "A child whose toy was bereaved, snake, a killing hit, Hitler, torture, paralysis, bodyguard, the first step taken by the child" have been developed. It is understood from the reasons of metaphors that students do not enjoy learning German and that German lesson is a traumatic process for them. Participant He "*The German lesson is like a child whose toy was bereaved for me. Because every time I attend a German lesson, I cry.*" stated with his analogy that he had entered into a negative emotion state in German lesson; participant 11e "*The German lesson is like a bodyguard for me because whenever I try to get along well with German lessons, it knocks.*" stated in fact that he wanted to love the German lesson and was not successful even though he tried to achieve this goal.

Table 8: Metaphors and Reasons for not Being Learned Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
War	Being unwinnable	Not being learned
An oily bowknot	Failure to learn	
A spiked casket	Inability to learn despite study	
Rowing in vain	Failure to learn	
Torture	Difficulty in learning	
Ocean	Failure to learn	
Nirvana	Failure to succeed	
Chinese	Incomprehension	
Dragon fruit	Failed to learn	
Language believed to be taught	Failure to learn	
Cigarette	Inability to use	
Language I don't need	Failure to learn	

In Table 8, in the category of not being learned, the metaphors of "war, an oily bowknot, a spiked casket, rowing in vain, torture, ocean, nirvana, Chinese, dragon fruit, language believed to be taught, cigarette, language I don't need" have been developed. When the

reasons of the metaphors are examined, it is understood that the students cannot learn German and therefore cannot use the language. Participant 9k *"German lesson is like a war for me. Because it is a reality that I know I cannot win."* stated that she had accepted the failure from the beginning due to her prejudice against German; participant 10k *"The German lesson is like the ocean for me because I get drowned in lessons no matter how much I want to learn."* stated that although she was interested in German, she could not learn.

Table 9: Metaphors and Reasons for Not Being Taught Well

Metaphor	Reason	Category
The language that I can not learn	Not being taught well	Not being taught well
What I forcibly endure	Not being taught well	
Boring lesson	Inefficient	
Torture	Inefficient	
Compulsory	Incomprehension	
Unnecessary	Incomprehension	
Empty lesson	Inefficient	
A difficult lesson	Inability to learn	
Horror movie	Not being taught	
Horrible movie	Inefficient	
Compulsory	Not being taught well	
An unnecessary lesson	Not being taught	

Table 9 contains the metaphors in the category of not being taught well, such as "the language I can not learn, what I forcibly endure, boring lesson, torture, compulsory, unnecessary, empty lesson, a difficult lesson, horror movie, horrible movie, compulsory, an unnecessary lesson". When the analogy of metaphors is analyzed, it is seen that the students associate the ne their negative perceptions about the German lesson to the qualifications of the teachers and the teaching mechanisms. Participant 10k *"German lesson is like a language which I cannot learn. Because we don't see the benefit of the German lesson at school."* stated that the lesson at school was not productive and the lesson was not instructive; participant 9e *"The German lesson is like what I endure forcibly because we don't have an effective instructor to teach German, so the lesson is boring and bad, so I don't like German."* stated that German lessons were inefficient and that she was bored because she was not an effective teaching.

Table 10: Metaphors and Reason for Being Important Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
An important lesson	Necessary	Being important
A valuable lesson	A new language, a new person	
Important for the future	Necessary	
Doner with buttermilk	Essential	
Chance	Opportunity for work	

In the category of being important in Table 10, the metaphors of "an important lesson, a valuable lesson, important for the future, doner mit buttermilk and chance" have been

developed. When the reasons of metaphors are examined, it is understood that students are eager to learn a second foreign language and are aware that learning a second foreign language will give them a privilege. Participant 12k *“German lessons are important to me. Because German is necessary for the future, for business life, expansion of the horizon and getting to know different people”* explained that German will be useful in business life in the future, knowing a second language will give an opportunity to know different cultures and people; participant 9k *“German lessons are like donuts for me because it is very necessary”* stated that knowing German is very important.

B. Categories of Metaphors Developed by Muğla 75. Yıl Science High School for German Lessons

Metaphors developed by the students of Muğla 75. Yıl Science High School on German lessons were categorized under 9 categories as *“complex, difficult, detailed, boring lesson, unnecessary lesson, inefficient, interested, break, important for the future”*. Each category is explained below.

Table 11: Metaphors and Reasons for Being Complex

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Ball of wool	Very complicated	Being complex
My relationships	Complex	
Space	There is no end	

In Table 11, the "ball of wool, my relationships and space" metaphors are developed in the complex category. When the reasons for metaphors are analyzed, it is seen that according to students German as a system has a complex feature. Participant 10e *“German lessons are like my relationships for me. Because the harder I work, the harder it gets.”* reported with his analogy that the complex structure of German cannot be understood, even though it is hard studied; participant 10k *“The German lesson is like space for me because the information is endless and impossible to learn.”* pointed out that too many rules and linguistic structures were taught in German lessons and therefore could not be learned.

Table 12: Metaphors and Reasons for Difficult Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Intelligence cube	Be difficult	Difficult
Black sea	Contrary and obstinate	
Pomegranate	Be difficult	

In the category of being difficult in Table 12, "intelligence cube, black sea and pomegranate" categories were developed. When the reasons for the metaphors are examined, it is understood that German is difficult according to the students. Participant 9e *“German lesson is like an intelligence cube for me. Because it is difficult to learn and we have to memorize some algorithms like in the cube of intelligence, as well as learning a lot of words and rules in German.”* emphasized that there are many rules to be memorized in German;

participant 10k *"The German lesson is like the Black Sea for me because it is contrary and obstinate."* stated that German has a difficult structure.

Table 13: Metaphors and Reasons for the Category of Being Detailed

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Desert	There is no end	Being detailed
Sky	There is no end	
A long way	Having a lot of topics	
Sea	Having a lot of topics	
Pomegranate	Be detailed	
Space	There is no end	

In the detailed category of Table 13, "desert, sky, a long way, sea, pomegranate and space" metaphors have been developed. When the reasons of the metaphors were examined, it was determined that there were too many details in the German lesson and that new subjects were taught constantly in the course. Participant 10k *"German lesson is like the sea to me. Because there is so much in class and I'm drowning."* emphasized that there are many topics to be learned in German; participant 10k *"The German lesson is like pomegranate for me because it looks as a whole from the outside, but the details are very much in it."* stated that there are many important details to be learned in German.

Table 14: Metaphors and Reason for Boring Lesson Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Watching golf	To be boring	Boring lesson
Spinach	To be boring	
Guest child	To be boring	
Celery	To be boring	

Table 14 presents the metaphors of "watching golf, spinach, guest child, celery" in the boring course category. When the analogy of metaphors is examined, it is seen that the students compare the German lesson to people and objects they do not like in daily life. Participant 10e *"German lesson is like spinach for me. Because the lesson was boring, I don't like it."* stated that she did not like to attend the lesson because the lesson was boring.

Table 15: Metaphors and Reasons for the Unnecessary Lesson Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Overshoe	Unnecessary	Unnecessary lesson
An unnecessary object	Not to utilize	
An unnecessary lesson	Not being asked in the exam	
Insignificant lesson	Not being asked in the exam	

In Table 15, in the category of being unnecessary, the overshoes, an unnecessary object, an unnecessary lesson, an insignificant lesson were developed. The students consider the German lesson unnecessary because they are not asked about the German lesson in the

university entrance exam and do not need German in their daily lives. Participant 11k *“German lesson is like an unnecessary lesson for me. Because it is not taken into consideration because it is not asked in the exam.”* stated that German is not considered because of not being among the questions asked in the exam; participant 10e *“The German lesson is like an overshoe for me because it will not come across me in any area of my life, which is extremely unnecessary.”* stated that she saw the foreign language, which she saw at school, unnecessary because she would not use it in her daily or business life.

Table 16: Metaphors and Reasons for the inefficient Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Torture	Not functional	Inefficient
Lesson that does not teach anything	Inefficient	
Foreign film	Inefficient	
Prayer	Inefficient	
Empty lesson	Inefficient	
Thief	Waste of time	
Free time	Inefficient	
Space	Inefficient	
Pool	Inefficient	

As shown in Table 16, the metaphors of “torture, lesson that doesn't teach anything, foreign film, prayer, empty lesson, thief, free time, space, pool” were developed in the category of inefficiency. With these metaphors, students emphasized the teacher dimension of the German lesson. When the reasons for the metaphors are examined, it is understood that the time spent for this course is a waste of time since there is no efficient teaching of German in the German course. Participant 11k *“German lesson is like torture for me because they teach unnecessary rules instead of teaching German in a way that we can communicate.”* stated that the functional aspect of the language was neglected and the formal aspect of the language was emphasized, which prevented students from communicating in German; participant 11k *“German lesson is like a prayer for me. Because I memorize a language that I don't know and take the exam.”* stated that she was trying not to understand and not to learn German, but only study to pass the exam.

Table 17: Metaphors and Reasons for interested Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Chocolate	Love very much	Interested
Kiwi	Love very much	
Book	Love very much	
Song	Enjoyable	
Crossword	Enjoyable	

In Table 17 the metaphors of “chocolate, kiwi, books, songs, crossword” were developed in the category of being interested. When the reasons for the metaphors are examined, it is understood that the students develop a positive perception of the German lesson.

Participant 10k *“German lesson is like reading a book for me. Because it feels more fluid as you progress.”* emphasized that the desire to learn German increased as she solved the structure of German and reached a certain level; participant 11k *“The German lesson is like a song for me because I enjoy vocalizing words.”* stated that it is enjoyable to speak German words phonetically and that German sounds good.

Table 18: Metaphors and Reasons for the Break Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Entertainment	Breathe	Break
School exit door	Rescuer	
The water I expect in Ramadan	Relaxing	
Dessert eaten after the dish	Have a rest	
A rest lesson	Breathe	

As seen in Table 18, the category of break includes the metaphors of "entertainment, school exit door, the water I expect in Ramadan, dessert eaten after the dish, a rest lesson". When the reasons of the metaphors are examined, it is understood that the students see the German lesson as a lesson where they can rest mentally, and this lesson is for them simpler than other lessons. Participant 9e *“German lesson is fun for me because it allows us to breathe between heavy lessons.”* stated that German lessons are fun for them because of the intensive lessons in the science high school curriculum; participant 10e *“German lesson is like the water I expect in Ramadan because we are distracting between heavy lessons and we rest.”* stated that he regards German lesson as a lesson to rest.

Table 19: Metaphors and Reasons for important for the future Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Key	Opening many doors	Important for the future
Bonus	Give opportunity	
Investment	To be useful for the future	
Pen	Beneficial	

As seen in Table 19, “key, bonus, investment, pen” metaphors have been developed in the category of being important for the future. When the reasons of the metaphors are examined, it can be said that the students are aware of the contributions that will be provided by knowing a second foreign language. Participant 10e *“German lesson is like a key for me. Because German is important to open many doors in the future.”* emphasized that German will be a language to be known in the future; participant 10k *“German lesson is like a bonus for me. Because I want to be an engineer and I think it will help me if I learn.”* stated that German is a very important language for her profession.

C. The Categories of Metaphors Developed by Turgut Reis Anatolian High School for German Lessons

The metaphors developed by the students of Turgut Reis Anatolian High School regarding the German lesson were categorized under 6 categories as “unnecessary, dislike, difficult, important, fun, learning new things”. Each category was explained below.

Table 20: Metaphors and Reasons for the Unnecessary Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Ineffective element	Not to be asked in the exam	Unnecessary
Unnecessary lesson	Not to be needed in the future	
Nonsense	Unnecessary	
Dessert before the meal	To be timeless	
Baklava	Not necessary	

As can be seen in Table 20, in the category of unnecessary the metaphors of “ ineffective element, unnecessary lesson, nonsense, dessert before the meal, baklava” have been developed. It is understood from the reasons of metaphors that students think that they will not need German after graduating from high school and that they will not have a period in which they will use German. Participant 10e *“German lesson is like an ineffective element for me. Because it isn’t be asked in the university exam.”* emphasized in his analogy that they do not care about this language since there are no questions about German in the university entrance exam; participant 11e *“the German lesson is like dessert for me before the meal. Because it is not right to start another language without learning a language.”* also made an assessment regarding the teaching of English. According to the students, teaching a second foreign language without learning English is not a correct foreign language policy. It is seen that the failure of the first foreign language has a negative effect on the teaching of the second foreign language of the students.

Table 21: Metaphors and Reasons for the Dislike Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Entering into the wet bathrooms floor with socks	Dislike	Dislike
Unbearable road	Boring	
Alcohol	Not to enjoy	
Nightmare	Dislike	
Persecution	Dislike	
The vegetables that my mother forcefully giving me	Not to enjoy	

In Table 21, the metaphors of “Entering into the wet bathrooms floor with socks, unbearable road, alcohol, nightmare, persecution, the vegetables that my mother forcefully giving me” were developed in the dislike category. When the analogy of metaphors is analyzed, it is understood that the motivation of students about German lesson is very low. Participant 11k *“The German lesson is like the vegetables that my mother forcefully giving me. Because I don’t like this lesson and I don’t think it will be useful for me.”* by

this analogy, it was determined that students' desire to learn German is very low and they are not aware that knowing German will benefit them.

Table 22: Metaphors and Reasons for Difficult Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Crossword	To be difficult	Difficult
Car without tire	Not to progress	
Never ending road	To be complex	
Space	Incomprehension	
Persecution	Incomprehension	

As seen in Table 22, there are metaphors of “crossword, car without tire, never ending road, space, persecution” in the category of being difficult. When the reasons for the metaphors are examined, it is understood that according to the students German is a difficult language to learn due to its complex structure. Participant 11e “*German lesson is like cruelty for me. Because I don’t understand anything from the lesson, the lesson is not efficient for me.*” stated that he could not learn anything in German lessons, for this reason, the German lesson was unpleasant; participant 9k “*German lesson is like a crossword for me. Because it’s hard to understand and read.*” stated that it is difficult to read and understand German text.

Table 23: Metaphors and Reasons for Being Important Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Bread and water	To be functional	Being important
Fortune	Be advantageous	
Beans and rice	Indispensable	

In the category of being important in Table 23, “bread and water, fortune, bean rice” metaphors have been developed. It is understood from the reasons of metaphors that students care about German lessons and are aware that it is advantageous to know a second foreign language. Participant 11e “*German lesson is like fortune for me. Because I think it is an advantage for me when I look for a job after I graduate from university.*” in her analogy, he stated that English is generally known by many people and knowing German besides English can be an advantage in job application.

Table 24: Metaphors and Reasons for the category fun

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Coffee and chocolate	Be enjoyable	
Chocolate milk	Be enjoyable	
Tea bagel	Be enjoyable	
My second mother	Be enjoyable	
Chocolate	Like	
The tramisu	Being happy	
To fishing	Like	
Chocolate cake	Like	

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Crossword	Like	Having fun
Being in a fast car	Enjoyable	
Water	Enjoyable	
The food I love to eat	Enjoyable	
Game	Being happy	
Gondola	Be enjoyable	
Dependent substance	Be enjoyable	
Chips	Be enjoyable	
Rosary	Like	
Play on the phone	Enjoyable	
Computer game	Be enjoyable	
Game lesson	Be enjoyable	
Ice cream	Be enjoyable	
The last lesson	Like	
Valuable person	Be enjoyable	
Fun fair	Be enjoyable	
Physical education lesson	Be enjoyable	
Happiness	Be enjoyable	
Amusement center	Be enjoyable	

As seen in Table 24, in the category of having fun “coffee and chocolate, chocolate milk, tea bagel, my second mother, chocolate, the tiramisu, to fishing, chocolate cake, crossword, being in a fast car, water, the food I love to eat, game, gondola, dependent, substance, chips, rosary, play on the phone, computer game, game lesson, ice cream, the last lesson, valuable person, fun fair, physical education lesson, happiness, amusement center” metaphors have been developed. When the reasons of the metaphors are examined, it is understood that German is an enjoyable and popular lesson according to the students. Participant 10k “*German lesson is like being in a fast car for me. Because while studying, both times passes fast and exciting and curious.*” stated that in the German lesson, students' curiosity and desire to learn German increased.

Table 25: Metaphors and Reasons for Learning New Things Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Book	Continuous learning	Learning new things
The door to infinity	Learning new things	
Training	Continuous learning	
Friend	Learning new things	
Close friend	Learning new things	
Waffle	Learning new things	

In Table 25, in the category of learning new things, "book, the door to infinity, training, friend, close friend, waffle" metaphors are developed. When the reasons for the metaphors are examined, it is understood that new information is constantly learned in the German lesson and this situation is evaluated positively by the students. Participant 11e “*German lesson is like a friend to me. Because it teaches me new things.*” it is seen with this analogy that a positive attitude towards German lesson has been developed and in each

lesson, they add new knowledge to their old German knowledge. Participant 9k *“German lessons are like waffles for me. Because when we combine the ingredients in it, a wonderful taste emerges just like German”* stated with expression that they love German lessons by combining new structures and words learned in each lesson in mind.

D. Categories of Metaphors Developed by Atatürk Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School for German Lessons

The metaphors developed by the students of Atatürk Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School for German lessons were categorized under 5 categories as “necessary / important, enjoyable, difficult, compulsory and like”. Each category is explained below.

Table 26: Metaphors and Reasons for the Necessary / Important Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Part of life	Since it is a tourism school	Necessary/Important
Necessity	Studying at the tourism school	
Diamond	Be valuable	
Life	Be important	
Native language breath	Be important	
Sun	Be useful	
Wealth	Be important	

In Table 26, the metaphors of “part of life, necessity, diamond, life, native language, breath, sun, wealth” were developed in the necessary/important category. When the reasons of the metaphors are examined, it can be said that according to the students’ German lessons are very necessary and important and they think that German is indispensable since they study at the tourism school. Participant 9e *“German lesson is like a part of life for me. Because the tourism school has a foreign language target.”* emphasized that German lessons are great of importance for his profession in the future; participant 9e *“The German lesson is like my native language Because I think it will work in my future life”* stated that they accept German not as a foreign language but also as their mother tongue, as they will use a foreign language as a result of their profession.

Table 27: Metaphors and Reasons for the enjoyable Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Honey	Enjoyable	Enjoyable
Good	Enjoyable	
Learning a good language	Like	
Beautiful	Enjoyable	
Physical education	Enjoyable	
Funny	Enjoyable	

As seen in Table 27, metaphors of “honey, good, learning good language, beautiful, physical education, funny” were developed in the enjoyable category. When the reasons for the metaphors are examined, it is understood that the students have a pleasant

German lesson. Participant 9e *“German lesson is like physical education for me. Because it is very enjoyable and very easy to learn.”* stated that he did not have difficulty while learning German in the course, but that he enjoyed the German learning process; participant 9e *“German lesson is fun for me. Because our teacher is trying to teach us German. And so I understand the lesson well.”* stated that their teachers made great efforts to teach German and to make the lesson efficient.

Table 28: Metaphors and Reasons for Difficult Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Maths	To be difficult	Difficult

Table 28 contains the metaphor of “mathematics” in the category of being difficult. They made a relationship between the German lesson and the math lesson and stated that German was as difficult as mathematics. Participant 9e *“German lesson is like math for me. Because it is very difficult. Two foreign languages are not tolerated.”* stated that it is difficult to learn a second foreign language in addition to a foreign language.

Table 29: Metaphors and Reasons for Being compulsory Course

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Obligation	Being compulsory	Being compulsory course

As can be seen in Table 29, there is a metaphor for “obligation” in the category of being compulsory courses. Participant 9e *“German lesson is like a obligation for me. Because I would like to learn Russian instead of German.”* stated that instead of being a compulsory foreign language, German should be an elective course and it is important to provide students with languages other than German as an alternative.

Table 30: Metaphors and Reasons for like Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Funny Maths Play a game Happiness	Be enjoyable Love Tasteful Love	Like

As seen in Table 30, “funny, mathematics, play a game, happiness” metaphors about like category have been developed. It was determined that the students developed a positive attitude towards the German lesson and enjoyed the lesson. Participant 9k *“German lesson is like math for me. Because I love German as much as I like mathematics lesson.”* from participant's statement it seems that their motivation for learning German is high.

E. Categories of Metaphors Developed by the Technology and Culture College High School for German Lessons

The metaphors developed by the Technology and Culture College High School students regarding the German lesson were categorized under 7 categories as “inefficient, pause, unnecessary, like, different from other languages, important, compulsory”. Each category is explained below.

Table 31: Metaphors and Reasons for the Inefficiency Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Empty lesson	Unproductive	Inefficient
Unnecessary	Unproductive	
Interesting	Course not being processed	
A big void	Course not being processed	
Boring lesson	Course not being processed	
Space	Course not being processed	
Insignificant	Course not being processed	

As seen in Table 31, the metaphors of “empty lesson, unnecessary, interesting, a big void, boring lesson, space, insignificant” related to inefficiency category have been developed. It is understood from the reason of metaphors that the weekly acquisitions stated in the German teaching program are not transferred to the students systematically in the German lesson, and activities such as watching videos and movies are performed instead of these achievements. Participant 9e “*German lesson seems unnecessary for me. Because it is a lesson that we know almost nothing, even though how many years we have studied*” stated that although they have been studying German for a long time, they cannot learn German; participant 9e “*German lessons seem interesting to me. Because we always watch movies.*” emphasized that they watched a movie in the lesson; participant 10k “*German lesson seems unimportant to me. Because it is 1 hour a week, the lesson is not taught and we cannot get efficiency.*” stated that due to the German lesson being only one hour per week, the German lessons were not given due importance.

Table 32: Metaphors and Reasons for the Pause Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
An activity that I relieve myself	Relaxation	Pause
Empty lesson	Not to teach a lesson	
Relaxing time	Not to teach a lesson	
A fun hour	Relaxing	
All kinds of activities we can rest	Relaxing	

As seen in Table 32, there are metaphors of “an activity that I relieve myself, empty lesson, a relaxing time, a fun hour, all kinds of activities we can relax” regarding the category of pause. When the reasons for the metaphors are examined, it is understood that the students see the German lesson as a break. Participant 9e “*The German lesson is like an activity for which I feel comfortable. Because it is not a very heavy lesson, I can rest my mind and*

body. " emphasized that they were physically and mentally rested in German lessons because they were not exposed to an intensive learning process; participant 10k *"German lesson is like a fun hour for me. Because we watch videos in the lesson, it makes me happy among the heavy lessons and helps me gather my energy."* stated that they saw the German lesson as a watch that they could rest between the heavy lessons, as the video was watched instead of teaching German.

Table 33: Metaphors and Reasons for the Unnecessary Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Meaningless	Unnecessary	Unnecessary
Ordinary	Unnecessary	
Insignificant	Unnecessary	

In Table 33, "meaningless, ordinary, insignificant" metaphors are developed in the category of unnecessary. It is understood from the reasons of metaphors that students consider German lesson as an unnecessary lesson. Participant 10e *"German lesson seems like ordinary to me. Because I don't think it will be very necessary."* stated that they are not aware of the advantages that second language education can provide; participant 10e *"The German lesson seems unimportant to me because no matter how much I want to learn German, it becomes ineffective because it is an one hour lesson offered to us."* stated that due to the fact that only one hour lesson per week is reserved for German, the yield could not be obtained, and accordingly it was considered insignificant.

Table 34: Metaphors and Reasons for the like Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Important	Like	Like
English	Like	
Funny	Like	
Flower	Enjoy	
Festival	Funny	

As seen in Table 34, "important, English, funny, flower, festival" metaphors were developed in the like category. When the reasons of the metaphors are analyzed, it is seen that the students develop a positive attitude towards the German lesson and enjoy the German lesson. Participant 9k *"German lesson is like a flower for me. Because it smells good as I smell, so I want to learn as I learn."* stated that she had interest and desire to learn German; participant 9k *"German lesson is like English to me. Because I love learning both."* stated that they liked German as well as English.

Table 35: Metaphors and Reasons for Different from Other Languages

Metaphor	Reason	Category
An interesting journey	Be different	Different from other languages
Setting a new sail	Having a different language	
The door to other countries	Different culture recognition	

In the category of being different from other languages in Table 35, “an interesting journey, setting a new sail, the door to other countries” metaphors have been developed. When the reasons of the metaphors are examined, it is understood that German has structurally different features from other languages, according to the students. Participant 9e “*German lesson is like an interesting journey for me. Because it has a different structure than other languages.*” stated that German is different from other languages they learned, such as English; participant 10e “*German lesson is like a door to other countries for me. Because knowing a new language means communicating with different people.*” stated that knowing a foreign language in general gives the opportunity to get to know different cultures.

Table 36: Metaphors and Reasons for Being Important Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
Important	Be useful in the future	Being important
Investment	Be useful in the future	
An important lesson	It is important to know the language	
Privilege	Adding value to the individual	
The main lesson	Be useful	

As seen in Table 36, “important, investment, an important lesson, privilege, the main lesson” metaphors were developed in the category of being important. When the reasons for the metaphors are examined, it is seen that the students think that knowing German will be useful in terms of their chosen professions in the future. Participant 9k “*German lesson is like a privilege for me. Because it makes us different from most people.*” emphasized that knowing German can make them advantageous by separating them from other people; participant 9e “*German lesson seems to be important to me. Because I will need it in the future.*” stated that they could use German in the future.

Table 37: Metaphors and Reasons for Compulsory Category

Metaphor	Reason	Category
An ordinary lesson	Compulsory	Compulsory

In the category of compulsory in Table 37 “an ordinary lesson” metaphor was developed. When the reason of the metaphor is examined, it is understood that the students perceive German as an ordinary lesson they see only because it is compulsory instead of being an important lesson for them. Participant 9e “*German lesson is like an ordinary lesson for me. Because it is a compulsory lesson I have seen at school.*” stated that German is a compulsory ordinary course.

4. Results and Discussion

In this study, which is to determine in Turkey the causes of positive and negative perceptions of high school students about German courses through metaphors according

to the high school type variable, data were obtained from high school students studying in five different school types.

The metaphors developed by Menteş social sciences high school students related to German lessons were gathered under 10 categories as “complex, very difficult, imperative, unloved, demanding effort, unnecessary, creating trauma, not being learned, important, not being taught well”. Metaphors developed by the students of Muğla 75. Yıl Science High School on German lessons were categorized under 9 categories as “complex, difficult, detailed, boring lesson, unnecessary lesson, inefficient, interested, break, important for the future”. The metaphors developed by the students of Turgut Reis Anatolian High School regarding the German lesson were categorized under 6 categories as “unnecessary, dislike, difficult, important, fun, learning new things”. The metaphors developed by the students of Atatürk Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School for German lessons were categorized under 5 categories as “necessary / important, enjoyable, difficult, compulsory and like”. The metaphors developed by the Technology and Culture College High School students regarding the German lesson were categorized under 7 categories as “inefficient, pause, unnecessary, like, different from other languages, important, compulsory”.

The categories created from metaphors developed in five school types are grouped as positive and negative categories below:

The “important” category developed by Menteş social sciences high school students regarding German lessons; The “interest”, important “categories developed by the 75th year high school students of Muğla; “Important, fun” categories developed by Turgut Reis Anatolian High School students; “Like, important, fun” categories developed by Atatürk Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School (Tourism) students; “Like, important” categories of Technology and Culture College High School students are positive categories. The categories of “difficult, obligation, disliked, demanding, unnecessary, creating trauma, not being learned, not being taught well; “Complex, difficult, elaborate, boring, unnecessary, break, inefficient” categories developed by 75th Year Science High School students in Muğla; “difficult, dislike, unnecessary categories developed by Turgut Reis Anatolian High School students; “difficult, obligation” categories developed by Atatürk Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School (Tourism) students; The “compulsory, unnecessary, break, inefficient, different” categories developed by the Technology and Culture High School students are negative categories. While the most negative categories developed regarding the German course are seen in the social sciences high school; positive categories were mostly obtained in Tourism High School.

Below are common categories developed for German lessons in all school types:

Common categories developed in German in all five school types are “complex, difficult, compulsory, unnecessary, important, inefficient”. The common thoughts of all the students participating in the research about the German lesson are that German is a structurally complex and difficult language, the German lesson is not a necessary lesson,

the lesson is inefficient. Despite these negative perceptions of students about German lessons, they also have positive perceptions about the importance of this lesson. Some students participating in the research think that German lessons can contribute to them in the future. As can be understood from the reasons of metaphors, the reasons for the negative perceptions of students in five school types regarding German lessons are; according to students, the structural features of German are complex, there are too many rules in German lessons, German is more difficult compared to English, they learn German because it is a compulsory lesson, they do not want German, German is not asked in the university entrance exam, therefore they see this lesson as unnecessary, and they can not learn German, because there is no effective German lesson at school. The reasons for the positive perceptions of the five school types of students regarding the German lesson were determined as the fact that knowing a second foreign language could give them an advantage in the future, to have an opportunity to get to know a different culture, to be aware of the advantages of knowing a second foreign language other than English, and to know German in terms of their chosen professions.

The perceptions of Atatürk vocational and technical Anatolian High School students, who are among the five schools where the data are obtained, differ from other schools. This school is tourism vocational high school. In this context, the students studying in Tourism High School think that, unlike the other four high schools, the German course is a necessary course and this language must be learned. On the other hand, four high school students stated that this lesson was not necessary and that there would be no loss for them. Likewise, Tourism High School students stated that they had interest in German lessons and they liked this lesson, while the other four high school students stated that they did not like German lessons. Therefore, the reason why tourism high school students have a positive perception about German lessons can be explained by their awareness that they will definitely use German in their professional life depending on the type of high school they study; the negative perceptions of other high school students can be explained by the fact that they are less likely to encounter German again after passing the class. In other words, because of the fact that the students of tourism high schools think that they will have the opportunity to use the language they learned in school, they have higher motivation and motivation for German lessons.

Students studying in science high school and private school stated that this course is like a break for them, depending on the activities such as video and movie screening instead of teaching activities that serve the purpose of the course in German lessons. Therefore, it can be said that it causes students to develop a negative perception about German lessons because the German language is not given due importance. Another criticism of private school students is that the German lesson time is only one hour. By supporting these findings, stated Kırmızı that the German lesson hours are insufficient and the German curriculum is heavy compared to this lesson time (2010). When a general evaluation is made based on the data obtained, it can be said that the reasons for the negative perceptions of the students regarding the German lesson are various reasons,

depending on the structure of the language, student-centered, teacher competence centered, exam system centered, and national language policy. The research group participating in the research have been learning English as a first foreign language from primary education. Therefore, after starting the German lesson, they have the opportunity to compare both languages. In this case, the structural differences such as the existing articles, adjectives, and verbs in German are relatively difficult for the students and the students evaluated learning inputs related to the structure of this language as difficult to understand. The development of a negative perception of learning input can be explained by the methods, techniques and strategies used by the teacher in the course. Therefore, in a study examining the opinions of Anatolian High School students about the teaching of German lesson, it was found that students mostly had problems in using German in daily life, students could learn German by using activities and visual materials, and technological tools such as computers and televisions (Kırmızı, 2010). Another reason of the students' negative perception about the German lesson may be that teachers do not use tools in the abstract language teaching process. As a matter of fact, in the study conducted to determine the problems experienced by teachers and students in the teaching of German grammar subjects in Anatolian high schools, it was concluded that the teachers did not use enough tools and materials other than the blackboard and textbooks in teaching their grammar, and that students found grammar subjects boring, and a few examples related to the subject were shown (Kırmızı, 2009). Depending on the method of presentation preferred in teaching grammar lessons, educational materials, tools and materials are also not used. The fact that teachers can use different methods, techniques, tools and necessities in the course is also related to the equipment of the schools. In a qualitative study in which the infrastructure and teacher competence in Anatolian high schools in Batman provinces and districts were investigated, it was stated that these high schools do not have a language classroom or language laboratory, and that this need is met with English teachers in high schools without German teachers (Balıcı, 2016). Another reason can be explained by the quality of German textbooks. There are no study groups and book diversity that can be an alternative in the preparation of German textbooks both in context and form. Therefore, in order to create alternatives for this purpose, the variety of books should be increased by the ministry instead of working on the same commissions and one book (Başaran, 2017: 32). In a study in which examined, textbooks in Turkey used for teaching German reached the conclusion that there are insufficient gains in achieving the objectives of text in some books (Genç & Ünver, 2012).

Another reason for their negative perceptions is that there are no questions from the German course in the university entrance exam. Students, who shape their learning processes with an exam focus, now focus on the lessons included in the exam, considering that the time allocated to a second foreign language will be a waste of time for them. As mentioned above, a great responsibility falls on the foreign language teachers besides the student in the language teaching process. While shaping the lesson setup of the teacher,

considering the students' interests and wishes, making a pleasant and efficient education can be determinant in the students' perceptions about the subject. In this context, in this study, some students stated that the lesson was boring, inefficient and empty because their teachers did not plan a teaching lesson. In a study on the behavior of Anatolian High School German teachers towards social and teaching methods, teachers do not use process-based measurement and evaluation methods such as portfolio and performance assignments, teachers use body language effectively, German teachers give importance to student and teacher communication, besides, teachers' creative lesson. It was concluded that they carried out and teachers were able to motivate students, students did not consider different learning strategies, and German teachers were not sufficient in creating a warm learning environment and being a guide (Demir & Genç: 2013).

5. Recommendations

Students' negative perceptions about the German course affect the language teaching process negatively. Therefore, as a result of this research, the following suggestions can be made regarding the teaching process of German lessons in high schools.

- Instead of making intensive knowledge and rule transfer in German lessons, priority should be given to the linguistic structures needed to develop communicative competence.
- In order to transform the negative perception that German is difficult and complex into positive, instead of explaining abstract complex German linguistic structures as purely learning in the course, a simpler linguistic use should be taught to students and students should be taught a sense of accomplishment.
- The motivations and language awareness of students should be developed by explaining the advantages of speaking German as a second foreign language in detail.
- Different effective methods and techniques should be used considering the individual differences, interests and wishes of the students.
- Instead of watching movies or videos that are not related to the target acquisitions during the lesson hours reserved for teaching German, lesson plans should be made to gain target behaviors in the German teaching programs. Thus, the value that it deserves, will be given to the German lesson, which is considered insignificant by the students.
- Educational materials that appeal to different senses should be used for the course to be efficient.
- German textbooks should be further diversified quantitatively.

About the Author

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